

Employee Perceptions of Privacy and Data Control in Workplace Wellness e-Health Programs

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Abstract—The adoption of IoT technology to improve wellness and health awareness in workplace environments is increasingly vital. However, the acceptance of such e-health interventions largely depends on employees’ perceptions of their value versus the privacy and security risks associated with data usage. Hence, addressing these concerns is paramount for fostering trust and ensuring the successful integration of technology. For this reason, this work explores the critical role of privacy in the workplace and examines how concepts of data control and ownership can improve the acceptance and effectiveness of IoT solutions. Leveraging insights from an online questionnaire with 524 participants from European countries, the obtained findings contribute to the existing literature by expanding the understanding of data control in workplace contexts and providing valuable insights for designing IoT-mediated e-health interventions that effectively address employees’ privacy concerns.

Index Terms—Smart Workplaces, Internet of Things, Privacy Concerns, Data Control

I. INTRODUCTION

Integrating IoT technology in various domains creates intelligent environments where people and technology collaborate to enhance user experience, habits, and behaviors [1]. Among these domains, the workplace stands out as a crucial environment undergoing digital transformation. Routines in the workplace significantly impact individuals’ physical and physiological health and wellness, presenting both challenges and opportunities for technology-driven solutions and e-health interventions [2]. As such, with the ability to identify and correct unhealthy behaviors, work environments are increasingly recognized as pivotal in promoting overall health [3]. The role of IoT and e-health in enhancing workers’ well-being lies in their ability to enhance individuals’ health perceptions. By leveraging IoT technology, workplaces can identify and address unhealthy habits, such as poor posture or inadequate hydration, thereby promoting both health and wellness [4]. Ultimately, integrating IoT and e-health interventions in workspaces can help raise individuals’ awareness of the impact of their habits on their overall well-being [5].

However, the literature highlights challenges in integrating IoT technologies into work environments, often stemming from users’ reluctance and aversion to proposed interventions, which can limit their effectiveness [6]. Acceptance of IoT in these environments is influenced by perceived value and

associated risks, as they present unique challenges regarding privacy and ethical concerns related to data collection [7]. Privacy concerns in these settings extend beyond typical security issues, encompassing social dimensions such as how third parties and companies may perceive data and its implications for productivity and work performance [8].

For this reason, in this work, we aim to explore the critical role of privacy concerns in the integration of technology in workplaces. Privacy is closely tied to the usage of captured data by third parties, the information derived from it, and who has access to or shares it. Hence, addressing privacy concerns involves preventing data disclosure and understanding how it affects employees’ beliefs and acceptance of technology. Nevertheless, existing literature lacks an expanded view of privacy, examining how employees’ perceptions would change if they had sole ownership and control over their data. To address this gap, we conducted an online questionnaire study involving 524 participants from European countries. The analysis focuses on the relationship between data control, privacy, and the perceived value of IoT technologies in workplaces for wellness interventions. This paper presents our findings, contributing valuable insights to the discourse on privacy and control in technology integration within work environments.

II. RELATED WORK

The integration of technology and IoT devices into the workplace holds significant potential, particularly in reshaping employee health through e-health initiatives. IoT devices can track a range of health indicators such as stress levels, physical activity, and environmental factors, contributing to more tailored and potentially effective wellness programs [9]. However, the adoption of these technologies introduces complex legal and ethical challenges. Key issues include privacy, security, the potential misuse of information, and the autonomy of employees [10], [11], [12]. Privacy concerns are particularly significant. Various studies have highlighted that employee acceptance of workplace technology is largely dependent on trust [13]. Masson et al. found persistent privacy concerns among participants using activity trackers at work, even in controlled experimental conditions [14]. Similarly, Chung et al. underscored the importance of clear data management policies and raised concerns about the use of third-party platforms

in wellness programs [15]. Nappi et al. also discussed the perceived risks and benefits of IoT in workplaces, stressing the need for increased awareness to address employees' reluctance and aversion [6]. The apprehension about privacy extends to fears of negative portrayal and disclosure of personal health information, leading to hesitancy in sharing data [8]. Concerns about how companies may measure activities and performance through these data contribute to feelings of surveillance, which exacerbates privacy worries [16]. In this sense, the fact that users typically do not own the data generated by IoT devices complicates their access to this information, and the lack of trust in how data is used contributes to user confusion. To foster acceptance of IoT in office environments, it is crucial to ensure transparency and grant users control over their data [17]. While privacy laws like the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are designed to secure these rights, the practical implementation of technology in workplaces often lacks clear communication and clarity [18], highlighting the need for improved policies and practices in the use of workplace technology.

Nonetheless, while privacy concerns significantly influence employees' attitudes towards technology, current research has not thoroughly explored how enhanced data control by employees might improve their views on technology and alleviate their privacy concerns, emphasizing that data ownership can be crucial for the successful integration of IoT in the workplace. Consequently, this study seeks to examine the effects of data control and ownership on technology acceptance, focusing not only on privacy issues but also on how perceptions may shift when users have increased authority over their data.

III. OBJECTIVES

As outlined in the introduction of this work, this study emphasizes the importance of addressing informational privacy threats and the significance of data control and ownership in guiding technology deployment in workplaces. The research focuses on two main objectives: evaluating the perceived value users assign to data collected through IoT devices and exploring how their perceptions shift when they maintain increased control over their data. Based on these focuses, two research questions have been formulated.

Research Question (RQ) 1: *What is the relationship between the perceived value of workplace-generated data and employee concerns about its use?*

The main concerns surrounding data capture in the workplace revolve around privacy invasion, contextualization of information, and potential misinterpretation of data. Employees' willingness to share their data with third parties is also a significant consideration. This RQ focuses on understanding how the perceived benefits of utilizing such data, such as improving workplace habits, correlate with the concerns regarding data sharing and personal information collection [19].

Research Question 2: *How does greater control and transparency over their data influence employee perception of workplace technology?*

When deploying technology, addressing the ownership of captured data remains a gap in current practices. Many IoT solutions lack user control over their data beyond browsing and exploring it. In the workplace context, the ownership of captured information is unclear, whether it should belong to the user, the employer, or the platforms used for data collection [20]. This RQ focuses on how notions of control influence technology perception.

IV. PROCEDURE AND METHODOLOGY

On the basis of the previous objectives and RQs, we designed an online study to understand the effect of addressed factors in the deployment of technology in the workplace. Online survey tools were chosen for the study due to their flexibility in gathering both quantitative and qualitative data, provided ethical considerations are taken into account [21], [22]. The questionnaire comprised four main sets of questions, including Likert-scale and multiple-choice questions, along with an open question for qualitative feedback. To begin with, participants were first introduced to the study and then asked about their initial insights on integrating smart technologies, perceived compatibility, and concerns about privacy and security risks. The items for measuring those factors were drawn from previously validated studies [23], [24]. Following the initial part of the survey, respondents provided demographic and socio-economic information before answering questions specific to the study's scope. A fictional use-case scenario was then presented, employing speculative design, a method exploring imaginary configurations of the world to understand users' perceptions and concerns [25]. The scenario depicted an e-health intervention in the workplace aimed at improving habits during work routines promoted by their companies. Respondents then answered questions regarding privacy requirements, data storage options, preferred data control levels, and general perceptions of emerging workplace technologies. Through the different sets of questions, statements and items were randomized to remove order bias [26]. Finally, the initial set of questions regarding participant insights on technology and privacy were repeated at the end of the survey to compare initial responses with those given after reflecting on the privacy-related aspects introduced by the speculative scenario, investigating potential changes in participants' answers [27].

A. Method and Sample

We recruited a total of 524 participants, both disseminating the survey among colleagues of the university, by snowball effect, on X (Twitter), and using Prolific Academic¹, a crowdsourcing platform that recruits participants for academic studies widely validated by the research community [28], [29]. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, with respondents compensated per the platform's policy. The recruitment was restricted to participants from the European Union (EU) and the United Kingdom (UK), although some participants indicated different nationalities. Furthermore, we applied a

¹<https://www.prolific.co/>

TABLE I
ITEMS AND CONSTRUCTS FOR THE PRE- AND POST-SCENARIO
EVALUATION. EXTRACTED FROM [23], [24].

Constructs	Item	Statement
Privacy Risks	PR1	If I use a smart work device, I would lose control over the privacy of my personal data.
	PR2	My personal information will be less confidential if I use a smart work device.
Security Risks	SR1	The security systems built into smart work devices are not strong enough to protect my information.
	SR2	Internet hackers might take control of my information if I use a smart work device.
Compatibility	COMP1	I feel that the smart work equipment fits my lifestyle.
	COMP2	I feel that the smart work equipment is compatible with my day-to-day needs.
	COMP3	I think that the smart work equipment will fit well into my work environment.
	COMP4	I think that the smart work products and applications are useful for the tasks I do at work.

screening process in which participants had to be actively working in office-based workplaces (e.g. in tertiary buildings or the service sector).

Demographically, 58.2 % of respondents were male, 41.4 % female, and 0.4 % identified as "other". The predominant age group was 22-40 years, and most had a bachelor's degree or higher. The survey included participants from 35 countries, mainly from Portugal (24.0 %), the United Kingdom (22.3 %), Poland (14.1 %), Italy (12.6 %), and Spain (7.8 %). Technologically, over half used wearable devices or health apps, and many engaged with other smart technologies, though 24.2 % did not use any of the specified technologies. While 67.9 % reported high technological knowledge, only 30.9 % had a similar understanding of the EU GDPR and privacy policies, indicating a significant gap in privacy knowledge among the technologically proficient.

V. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained after evaluating the responses to the introduced survey. Before doing so, we first analyze whether the responses to the repeated set of questions regarding the initial perception of IoT technologies present remarkable variances when inquired before and after describing the speculative scenario (Pre-Post scenario description). Then, we focus on the evaluation of the questions concerning the speculative scenario and the concepts of data control and ownership.

A. Pre-Post scenario questions

This evaluation compares participants' responses to questions about the use of IoT devices for wellness promotion at work, asked at the beginning and end of the survey. These items were grouped into three constructs: (i) Privacy Risks (PR), (ii) Security Risks (SR), and (iii) Compatibility (COMP). Each construct is assessed through specific statements to gauge participants' attitudes and perceptions towards smart work devices, included in Table I.

Fig. 1. Mean values for each of the factors included in PR, SR and COMP for the pre and post-scenario questions.

The results are compared in Figure 1. Their mean scores illustrate that, in the case of privacy-related aspects, concerns were higher about losing control over personal data ($PR1$ pre = 3.11, post = 3.10 & $PR2$ pre = 3.30, post = 3.35) than security breaches ($SR1$ pre = 2.97, post = 3.06 & $SR2$ pre = 3.04, post = 3.08). Despite perceived risks, compatibility mean scores showed favourable perceptions of smart devices in the workplace ($COMP1$ pre = 3.41, post = 3.40 & $COMP2$ pre = 3.42, post = 3.45 & $COMP3$ pre = 3.41, post = 3.38 & $COMP4$ pre = 3.40, post = 3.34). In light of them, participants generally viewed smart devices positively as COMP is higher than perceived risks. Furthermore, no significant differences were found between the pre- and post-scenario results, confirmed by a high Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.97$, $p < 0.0001$) and a non-significant paired t-test ($t(7) = 0.7347$, $p = 0.4864$). This indicates that the speculative scenario did not significantly alter participants' opinions or raise additional awareness about information control and privacy in the survey context and, therefore, without influencing the user's answers.

B. Speculative scenario

After this initial set of questions, participants were placed in the speculative scenario where their companies launched a wellness promotion campaign using IoT technologies and were asked about their initial reactions to participating in such an intervention. The findings show varied responses: 36.3 % (N=190 out of 524) would discuss with colleagues before deciding; 33.2 % (N=174) would join immediately; 17.6 % (N=92) would wait and observe others before joining; and only 13 % (N=68) would choose not to participate. This shows a high interest among the majority of respondents. Then, participants were asked to select from a list the top three aspects that they consider the most valuable for them in the described system (i.e. the provided smart devices for health tracking). The included options and the obtained responses are summarized in Table II.

A close examination of participants' responses reveals that the majority value the system's usefulness (54.00 %). Privacy concerns were also prominent, with 45.00 % of participants

TABLE II
OBTAINED RESPONSES TO THE QUESTION "What do you value most when it comes to using such a system? (i.e. the provided smart devices)".
RESPONDENTS WERE ASKED TO SELECT THREE OPTIONS OUT OF THE SEVEN GIVEN.

I Value appreciate...	Freq.	%
That the system is actually beneficial to me or my health.	283	54.00 %
That the system is secure and privacy-aware (i.e your personal information will not be compromised).	236	45.00 %
That I can understand how the system works, what kind of information it collects, which is the use of the collected data and who has access to them.	232	44.30 %
That my personal data is only used for the purpose for which it is collected.	227	43.30 %
That the collected data does not cause any harm to me, neither personally nor professionally.	224	42.70 %
That I can decide which of the data collected by the system is public or private, or to whom it is shared.	188	35.90 %
That the system is efficient enough without requiring much attention or time from me.	182	34.70 %

TABLE III
AVERAGE RESULTS TO THE QUESTION *In your opinion...Who should be responsible for the storage and security of the data that you produce in the workplace, and that is collected by the intelligent system?*". EACH ITEM WAS RATED FROM 1 (COMPLETELY DISAGREE) TO 5 (COMPLETELY AGREE).

Statement	MEAN	SD
All data should remain under my ownership, and I will be the only person that can grant access to third parties of certain data I produce.	4.00	1.15
All data that I produce should remain under my ownership but visible to interested entities, as long as this data can not be linked to me and only for the sake of my health.	3.40	1.25
All data that I produce should remain under the ownership of my company/organization, as long as these data can not be linked to me.	3.15	1.24
All data that I produce should remain under my ownership but visible to the healthcare company of the organization where I work.	3.15	1.23
All data that I produce should remain under my ownership but visible to my company/organization.	3.09	1.24
All data that I produce should remain under the ownership of my company/organization since they are the health campaign promoters.	2.48	1.26

prioritizing the security and specific use of their data, and 44.30% valuing transparency in how data is managed, which could lead to potential conflicts of interest between employees and employers [15]. This conflict arises from data interpretation and potential misuse, especially in workplace settings where data may relate to productivity or performance. For this reason, 43.30% of participants insisted that personal data be used solely for its intended purpose, while 42.70% stressed that the information should not harm them personally or professionally. The control over whether data is public or private was less prevalent, selected by only 35.90%, possibly due to reluctance to make their data public at first. The least prioritized aspects were the system's initial functionality and efficiency, deemed crucial by only 34.70% of respondents.

The analysis of the reported data reveals that participants prioritize balancing the risks of data sharing with third parties against the perceived benefits and value of the system collecting this data. For this reason, the next question of the survey addressed specifically who should have the final responsibility for the data, asking participants to rate their agreement with various statements about who should own the data and who should access it from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree). The averages of their responses are included in Table III. The results show a strong preference among participants for retaining ownership and control over their data, with 240 respondents fully agreeing that all data should remain under their ownership and that they should decide who can access it and rating this statement with a 5, resulting in a mean value of 4.00 (SD 1.15) among all the responses. In contrast, the idea of company ownership of data was unpopular, with 155 respondents strongly disagreeing, reflected in a low average agreement score of 2.48 (SD 1.26).

However, willingness to share data with healthcare companies and organizations increased slightly when participants retained ownership, scoring averages of 3.15 (SD 1.23) and 3.09 (SD 1.24), respectively. Interestingly, the acceptance of company ownership rose to 3.15 (SD 1.24) when data anonymization was assured, suggesting a greater openness to sharing anonymized data for health purposes, with an increased score of 3.40 (SD 1.25). This reflects ongoing concerns about privacy and the personal or productivity-related information contained within the data [19]. Overall, participants expressed that they view the visibility of their information by other entities or health companies positively only if the data remains under their control or is anonymized, enhancing the perceived value of the system. Besides, they clearly preferred having direct control over their data rather than having it managed by their companies, indicating that privacy and the conditions under which data is visible to third parties hinge critically on their ability to control their own data.

Finally, to conclude the set of questions directly related to the speculative scenario, we put the focus on investigating those general aspects that respondents consider more valuable for using the described IoT system for e-health at the workplace. We asked respondents to rate various statements from 1 to 5, according to their level of agreement or disagreement with each of them. The obtained average results are included in Table IV. The most valued feature was the system's customization capabilities, which achieved the highest average score of 4.06 (SD=0.89). Usability, particularly the ability to tailor system-user interactions, also scored highly, with an average of 3.71 (SD=0.93). In line with the findings of the previous questions, continuous data collection was viewed negatively, with a mean score of 2.53 (SD=1.27). Similarly, participants

TABLE IV
AVERAGE RESULTS FOR RATING THE INCLUDED ITEMS FROM 1 (COMPLETELY DISAGREE) TO 5 (COMPLETELY AGREE).

Statement	MEAN	SD
The intelligent system must have the ability to be customized according to my specific needs.	4.06	0.89
The intelligent system can be located locally or remotely, as long as the protection of the collected data is regulated or I have control over them.	3.84	0.99
The intelligent system must be able to interact with me in a tailored manner, e.g. only when I have availability.	3.71	0.93
The intelligent system must be located close to me, in a local device I own, so that the collected data are not stored on external devices (e.g. cloud servers my company own) that I can not control.	3.45	1.13
The intelligent system must be always on, collecting my data at all times.	2.53	1.27
The intelligent system must be remotely located so that the collected data are stored on external devices (e.g. cloud servers my company own) that I can not control.	2.38	1.12

strongly opposed external data storage on remote servers they couldn't control, resulting in a low score of 2.38 (SD=1.12), whereas data storage on local devices was favored, receiving a score of 3.45 (SD=1.13). The preference for local control extended to hosting the system either remotely or locally, as long as control over the data was maintained, which scored 3.84 (SD=0.99). These findings confirm a strong preference for users to manage data directly, aligning with previous insights about the importance of control over data and systems.

To conclude the survey, 80 participants provided voluntary feedback on the open question, highlighting concerns about privacy invasion and potential data misuse by employers, including fears of being judged, monitored, or having their data used inappropriately [20]. Despite appreciating the system's comfort and practicality, participants emphasized the need to address potential harms, and concerns remained about its potential to track work hours or sell personal information. These qualitative insights, along with quantitative data, underscore the importance of tackling privacy and data control issues to enhance the acceptance of IoT technology in workplace wellness programs.

C. Limitations

Before concluding, it is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of this study. First, the findings are based on responses from a fictional scenario, which might not directly translate to real-world situations. Secondly, participants' responses could be biased by their prior technology use and experiences. Besides, the study also had a limited demographic scope, primarily involving participants from the EU and UK with medium-to-high technological backgrounds, potentially excluding those less familiar with technology. Additionally, the results may not be generalizable beyond these regions due to cultural and regulatory differences. Therefore, while interpreting the conclusions within the context of these constraints, it is important to note that this study provides foundational, exploratory insights into user concerns and needs on how technologies are perceived in the workplace context.

VI. DISCUSSION

The literature has generally overlooked data control and ownership in IoT implementations. This is reflected on the traditional implementation of IoT systems, that often centralize

data processing on external servers, distancing users from their data. Consistent with previous research, our study illuminates significant barriers in data gathering within work environments and their implications, highlighting that privacy and security risks negatively affect perceptions of IoT-mediated workplace wellness e-health programs. A primary concern is the potential misuse of data, representing the critical need for assurances that data will not be compromised. Responding to RQ1, the study reveals that the perception of data collection in the workplace hinges on the cost-benefit ratio of such data generation. Participants were more inclined to share data with healthcare companies or other entities when they retained control and anonymity of their data. The findings underscore the importance of data control and ownership, with a clear preference against allowing companies complete control over their data. Consequently, for RQ2, the results show a strong preference for storing data on local devices, where participants can maintain direct control rather than on remote servers. Participants stressed the necessity of having complete authority over their data and the ability to decide who accesses it. Overall, the desire for control and the ability to personalize the system significantly affect how IoT technologies are perceived in the workplace.

For this reason, our contribution extends the concept of privacy to the ability of the user to be the owner of the information they generate and to determine how, when, and to whom this personal information can be disclosed. Furthermore, the conducted research stresses the importance of addressing the users' role within the system, as well as the control and customization options users expect to have. These are significant factors to consider to fit their needs and expectations in those intelligent environments and involve employees in decisions about data collection and usage. Emerging technologies like edge computing and privacy-by-design approaches are vital in addressing data control and ownership concerns in e-health interventions in the workplace, minimizing dependence on external servers, enhancing individual control over data and ensuring that privacy considerations are embedded throughout the design process. By combining these approaches, work environments can prioritize data control, ownership, and privacy, enhancing user confidence, and fostering the adoption and acceptance of IoT technologies and increasing the potential outcomes of wellness programs.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

To enhance e-health integration in the workplace, it is essential to comprehend and address employee perceptions and needs. This work, which studied 524 responses from various European locations to an online survey, explored the impact of IoT technology integration through an speculative scenario where companies initiated an e-health campaign using IoT devices. The quantitative analysis of the data highlights significant concerns; privacy issues notably decrease participants' willingness to embrace smart technologies at work. The study reveals that participants' acceptance of technology and data collection is contingent on a favorable cost-benefit analysis of the system. Importantly, when employees retain control and ownership over their data, ensuring exclusive access and management rights, their confidence in the technology and its data use purposes significantly increases. These findings are consistent with the current literature, yet our research extends the definition of privacy to encompass the user's ownership of their data and their authority to dictate its usage, timing, and sharing parameters. Furthermore, it emphasizes the necessity of acknowledging the user's expectations for data control. These elements are crucial for creating intelligent environments that are in harmony with user needs and preferences. Therefore, our study enriches the existing knowledge by offering a more nuanced understanding of employee perceptions regarding data control and ownership in the workplace and settles the conceptual basis when deploying IoT devices in a human-centric work environment.

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